

A novel rainwater circular solution as a distributed intervention to increase the resilience of water scarce decentralized communities: A Real World Demonstration in the Mykonos Mediterranean Island

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Introduction

Water is essential for the survival and well-being of humanity and plays a vital role in sustainable development. By continuing our “business as usual” model in freshwater consumption, the global demand for freshwater might exceed our viable resources by 40% in 2030 (Tahir et al., 2019). But by embracing Circular Economy (CE) principles and by supporting technological innovation, the linear model that assumes that water resources are abundant, available, and cheap to dispose, can be abandoned and instead the focus is transferred on preserving the natural capital and securing water supply where resources are scarce. The closure of this loop leads to a tighter nexus adding inter-connections that improve the autonomy and resilience at every level of the entire water management system (Makropoulos et al., 2018). As water scarcity becomes more prevalent in semi-arid regions, new circular water management systems and actions establishing CE strategies in the water sector are of significant relevance for a sustainable environmental and economic development of these regions. Especially for the Mediterranean Basin, where high temperatures and minimal rainfall characterize the summer climate (Ulbrich et al., 2012), recent studies point to future trends towards even drier conditions with increased frequency of extreme rainfall events (Giorgi & Lionello, 2008). The total precipitation is expected to decrease, as longer dry spells and reduced rainfall intensity have been observed (Cramer et al., 2022). Therefore, these regions suffer from the limitation and irregular distribution of their water reserves, while the increasing touristic activities during the summer season put additional stress on their water supplies, both in terms of quantity and quality. The Mediterranean islands face even greater challenges and experience more severe water scarcity issues due to their relatively smaller size and isolation. To address such issues, transformative adaptation water management solutions, within the concept of CE are urgently required to increase community resilience, to enable effective and far-reaching changes, to adapt to the projected climate change and to carry out a sustainable transition.

Material and methods

Within this context, a residential-scale prototype decentralised, flexible and autonomous rainwater harvesting, storage and recovery system has been developed and implemented in the highly touristic Mediterranean island of Mykonos (Cyclades, Greece). This system demonstrates how a residential rainwater collection system can be upgraded to optimise the low-cost rainwater harvesting infrastructure and the natural services provided by the subsurface geological conditions, with a positive impact on the environment. The principal concept is to store excess water during the winter months to reuse it in the summer that is to maximise the existence of the natural resource throughout the year. To achieve this, an innovative system comprising from two separate but interrelated subsystems has been designed, constructed, and tested, in order to enhance the buffering against evaporation and water loss and extend water availability towards the dry season. In particular: (1) A *Residential rainwater harvesting system* that collects rainwater from the rooftops, sends it with gravity in a tank and is reusing it for domestic purposes in the local residences. (2) An *Aquifer storage and recovery system*, in which rainwater is collected through two methods: (a) The **surface runoff** of the impermeable surfaces of the site is collected in the wet period, stored in a tank and reused for irrigation purposes during the dry period; excess water is used to recharge the aquifer (subsurface “basin”) in the optimum site location identified through geophysical surveys, from which water is recovered (through an artificial recharge (AR) well - W_{AR}) and reused for irrigation in the dry period. (b) Water is also collected through a **bioswale system**, an open-channel linear drainage system, stored in an open tank and excess water is recharged in the subsurface “basin” to be recovered and reused in the dry period. When water is needed for irrigation, this is recovered from the AR well first and the open tank second. When water is recovered in the AR well, this is sent back to the open tank so that it is always full. The monitoring of the rainwater collection systems was achieved by online systems (pH, EC, water level) and sampling campaigns (standard physicochemical parameters, heavy metals, major ions, pathogens). In order to

provide optimized water management solutions for the wet and dry seasons, the behaviour of the aquifer was monitored and simulated, and the storage and retention capacity of recharged water was assessed. For this, water level fluctuations of the W_{AR} along with meteorological observations were studied and processed for a period of two consecutive seasons: 2020-21 and 2021-22.

Results and discussion

From the processed data, we concluded that the partitioning between “wet” and “dry” seasons starts earlier in March (instead of June) due to the increasing forcing of daily air temperatures, irrespective of the spring (March – May) rainfall totals. In the dry season, high linear correlation coefficients ($r > 0.9$, $p < 0.001$) between air temperature and subsurface water level suggest that simple linear regression models can efficiently describe the diel water level fluctuations. Furthermore, the low values of the linear regression slope coefficients for both dry seasons provide firm evidence of the retention capacity of the aquifer. Despite the spring (March-April) rainfalls during the 2020 / 2021 dry season, W_{AR} water level continued its linear drop. Therefore, all excess water stored in the other installations (bioswale, surfaces, etc.) could be injected into the W_{AR} before or during spring (March – May) rainfall events to prolong the subsurface aquifer water retention and recovery.

During the wet season, the simulation showed a nonlinear response to the combined forcing of rainfall and precipitation, which was expected as the lagged response of W_{AR} water level (WL) varied between 10 hours to 10 days depending on the aquifer recharge mechanism that was activated. Field data suggested that the longest lags of W_{AR} water level response to rainfall occurred at the start of wet season and that the highest cross correlation between WL and rainfall was reached after 25 days due to the large spatial variability of the rainfall events. The simulation was achieved through Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) between rainfall, temperature and the W_{AR} WL for the 2021-2022 wet season. Thus, even in the wet season the effect of local rainfall on water level was substantially reduced highlighting the significance of air temperatures in the future use of subsurface water storage and recovery systems in the Mediterranean semi-arid regions.

To withdraw water volumes of 1m^3 during late wet season from the subsurface aquifer for domestic or agricultural use is possible and supported by both the simulation model and the slug test. To inject excess water from other installations (bioswale, surface runoff, roof tops) before rainfall during the early dry season (March – May) shall result in higher retention capacity and allow the use of small amounts of water during the dry season. This management practice has the additional advantage of reducing the conductivity and turbidity values, and hence improves the quality of the water stored in the aquifer.

With regard to the water quality, the irrigation water, collected from surface runoffs shows EC values greater than $750\ \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, classified in category C3-S1, in Wilcox diagram, in terms of salinity risk (moderate with limited irrigation in poorly drained soils). This is an average quality complying with our needs for the irrigation of the on-site crops.

Conclusions

The optimised approach of collecting and storing rainwater from rainfall events to maximise the utilization of natural water resources and to extend water availability well into the dry season for domestic and agricultural water reuse, can clearly support the protection, environmental regeneration and financial sustainability of the area. It was also proven that rainwater can be stored and gradually recovered from the subsurface, constituting an autonomous, flexible and decentralised water recovery system tested to be suitable in real world environments and potentially be upscaled and replicated in similar water scarce areas. Regarding the rainwater collection systems, we concluded that the quality of water is quite stable and satisfactory in terms of electrical conductivity and sodium hazard. No significant variation is noticed. Thus, this water management schemes could be considered as a ‘climate-proofed’ solution and be part of the reuse/circular economy portfolio. We argue that these types of solutions can form part of flexible and resilient regional climate change adaptation pathways – particularly suitable for the European South.

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